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The Use of Anglicisms in Various Thematic Fields: An Analysis Based on the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual**

Abstract

This piece of research presents an analysis of the use of anglicisms in the Spanish press at the beginning of the 21st century. Specifically, it concentrates on their distribution in texts belonging to different thematic domains. Thus, the purpose of this study is to establish a ranking of specialised fields in terms of the frequency with which anglicisms are employed in them. In order to do so, the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual (CREA)*, compiled by the Real Academia Española, is used as the source for texts, which supports the reliability and representativeness of the present work.

1. Introduction

The presence of anglicisms in the Spanish language constitutes a recurrent object of linguistic study nowadays. Many scholars have focused on the use of English loanwords in certain specific thematic areas, and even comparative pieces of research on various domains have been published (see section 2). However, in relation to specialised fields, an in-depth analysis of the situation of Spanish anglicisms at the beginning of the 21st century in a dynamic source such as the press, using large numbers of texts provided by an online corpus, was still to be done.

As a matter of fact, the use of existing language databases to study linguistic phenomena such as the one that will be dealt with in this article is a major advance in terms of reliability and representativeness. In this case, the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual (CREA)*, compiled by the Real Academia Española and containing a large sample of texts classified in 93 different thematic areas, has been considered to be an appropriate source to carry out a study of anglicisms in the Spanish press (Oncins-Martínez 2012).¹

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Within this framework, the present study aims to classify the fields contained in the CREA in terms of the frequency with which anglicisms are employed in them. Moreover, the following hypothesis is tested: *Sports, computing, economics, advertising, and tourism are the topics in which anglicisms are more frequently employed*. This selection of thematic areas has been made in accordance with the existing amount of literature devoted to the study of anglicisms in different specialised fields (see section 2).

2. Research to date

The main thematic area concerning anglicisms in the 22nd edition of the *Diccionario de la lengua española (DRAE)*, i.e. sports, as Domínguez Mejías (2002) reveals, is dealt with in Fernández García (1971). Specifically, he focuses on the word *sport* and its compounds and derivatives, as well as on other words belonging to this field (such as *golf, tennis, hockey, basket-ball, lawn-tennis, and fútbol* [original spelling]).

Other authors also delve into the use of anglicisms in the field of sports. Rodríguez Medina (2014) explores the influence of the English language in the vocabulary related to the sport activities that are practiced in Spanish gyms. Rodríguez González (2012) reports on several types of linguistic as well as socio-linguistic variation that are present in anglicisms belonging to the area of sports: (i) dialectal, (ii) lexical and morphological, (iii) stylistic and semantic – the last one including: lexical, graphematic, orthographic, phonological, and morpho-phonological. Balteiro Fernández (2011) carries out a contrastive analysis of the appearance of English forms in the *DRAE*, the *Nuevo diccionario de anglicismos* (Rodríguez and Lillo 1997) and the *CREA*. Finally, Mayoral Asensio (1997) considers stylistic variation as a reason why anglicisms survive in the vocabulary of sports (since there is a need to use a number of synonyms; for instance, *corner / saque de esquina*).

As far as English loanwords employed in the domain of economics are concerned, there is a great amount of literature that concentrates on this topic. Some treatments are PhD theses, such as Cece (2016), Vélez Barreiro (2003), Diéguez Morales (2003), and Alejo González ([1993] 2002).

In addition to these dissertations, numerous articles focus on the use of anglicisms in this field. Orts Llopis and Almela Sánchez-Lafuente (2009) offer an analysis as well as a description of the many English loanwords that have entered Spanish economic discourse during the Global Systemic Crisis. Later, in Orts Llopis and Almela Sánchez-Lafuente (2012, 89), the authors delve into the topic of their previous paper, but go further to develop “a system of lexical selection that reunites, analyzes and explains a representative group of real data”.

With regard to the origin of neological terms in the area of economics,² Russo (2002) highlights that most of them are created in English, and Spanish specialists take them as loanwords or calque them. Six years later, the same author, Russo (2008), presents a very interesting analysis of the words *resilience* in English and *resiliencia* in Spanish within texts belonging to the domain of economics.

Considering the legal discursive field, Orts Llopis (2005, 49) highlights that “in the areas of finance and mercantile law most of the coinages are actually in English”. According to Sánchez-Reyes Peñamaría and Durán Martínez (2002, 252), there are three particular areas in which anglicisms are more commonly employed: “el Derecho Mercantil, el Derecho Internacional y el Derecho Económico”. Orts Llopis (2006) goes in depth into the first of these three branches, focusing on the import-export lexicon.

Moving on to the field of advertising, van Hooft Comajuncosas (2006) deals with the anglicisms found in the advertisements included in the Spanish edition of *Elle*, a magazine addressed to young and educated women. Using the same magazine but considering this time the editions from four other Western European countries too (Belgium, France, Germany, and the Netherlands), Gerritsen et al. (2010) aim to check whether the same advertisement in English, on the one hand, and in the local language, on the other hand, performs a different effect on the target audience. Finally, a third related article (Gerritsen et al. 2007) answers a series of detailed research questions on the use of anglicisms in the adverts included in *Elle* magazine, carrying out a comparison of the editions published in several countries.

With respect to anglicisms in TV advertisements, González Cruz (2015, 339) presents a study of “a corpus of commercials recorded from four Spanish TV channels with high audience shares between 2013 and 2015”. These adverts are related to three leisure fields: *technology*, *entertainment*, and *food and drink*. In the light of her findings, González Cruz (2015, 350) confirms “the noticeable presence of English in this influential mass media”, highlighting “the prestige and sense of modernity³ associated to English and the important role this language seems to play for linguistic creativity and lexical innovation”. Most recently, García Morales et al. (2016) examine anglicisms in Spanish TV advertisements as recorded between 2013 and 2015.

The area of computing has also been dealt with in terms of the use of English loanwords. Cerdá Redondo et al. (2005) undertake a preliminary study of anglicisms related to the field of computer science (establishing a series of methodological bases that will be utilized throughout the development of their planned research project), which is later complemented by a more in-depth analysis presented in Díez Prados et al. (2007), where the authors discuss the process of integration that English loanwords undergo after entering the Spanish computing lexicon. To this end, and following Alejo (1998), they group anglicisms into three

different categories depending on their degree of assimilation: integrated loans, non-integrated loans, and code-switches. This same typology is proposed by Gallench and Posteguillo Gómez (2001, 243), whose work aims “to identify and describe the series of English borrowings and Spanish-into-English code-switches which take place in Spanish specialized discourse in the specific field of computer technology”. To achieve this purpose, the authors carry out an analysis of 17 articles extracted from *Web, la revista de los usuarios de Internet*, an example of “Spanish computer specialised publications for professional and computer users in non-academic format and register” (Gallench and Posteguillo Gómez 2001, 243), and conclude that “the systematic use of these English borrowings and code-switches is (...) a representative linguistic device of these non-academic written texts” (Gallench and Posteguillo Gómez 2001, 251). Posteguillo (2002), who provides some data on the technological level of the Internet field, offers an account of the terminological layer, and quotes Shortis (2001) to explain the two main terminological creation processes that operate in the English language – namely, morphological ones and semantic ones.

A contrastive study of the impact of English on computing texts from the European and Mexican varieties of Spanish is laid out by Smessaert (2012) in her Master’s dissertation. This author reports on the terminological influence of the English language on the written press in Spain and Mexico, focusing on the field of computing, specifically on webmail and social networks. She compares the data obtained from two corpora,⁴ each from a different geographical area.

In her study on computing anglicisms in the Spanish press (1990–2004), Andersson (2008) demonstrates, on the grounds of her results, that there is not a decrease in the use of pure anglicisms in favour of their Spanish translations or of hybrid forms throughout the time span she analyses.

Another area that has been approached in relation to the use of anglicisms is fashion. With respect to this topic, Balteiro Fernández (2014) draws on the influence of English on the Spanish language of fashion, specifically on the relevant role played by *-ing* forms. Diez-Arroyo (2016) approaches the euphemistic value of anglicisms in Spanish fashion magazines, which “regard stylistic choices as a persuasive strategy to reach and appeal to their wide readership. Journalists have found in Anglicisms the perfect elements to perform this rhetorical function” (2016, 38).

Other areas that have been explored in relation to the presence of English loanwords are music (Vigara Tauste 2007; Olivares Baños 2009), health sciences (Gutiérrez Rodilla 1997; Alcaraz Ariza 1998; Navarro 2002; 2008), and the cinematographic language (Guzmán González 1986; Rodríguez Segura 1998; García Morales 2009).

Lastly here, a couple of studies that examine anglicisms in more than one specialised field will be adverted to. Tejedor Martínez et al. (2006) concentrate on the areas of economics, computing, and tourism.⁵ Taking from their findings,

the authors claim that “se observan ciertas similitudes entre los tres ámbitos del español para fines específicos examinados” (Tejedor Martínez et al. 2006, 373). Also, it is worth mentioning an interesting work on anglicisms in the fields of computer science, medicine, tourism, and science and technology. Basing their analysis on a body of authentic texts, de la Cruz Cabanillas and Tejedor Martínez (2012) build a textual corpus covering several technical domains and including documents from different registers. Their “textual corpus of specialised disciplines stands at around 867,000 words” (de la Cruz Cabanillas and Tejedor Martínez 2012, 97). In addition, they design a database called ANGLICOR, where they store the following “data about every recorded item extracted from the corpus” (de la Cruz Cabanillas and Tejedor Martínez 2012, 98): definition, gender, number, etymology, presence or absence in Spanish dictionaries, source, graphic marks, semantic field, socio-pragmatic details, genre, and topic. “The total number of items included in the database is 4,607” (de la Cruz Cabanillas and Tejedor Martínez 2012, 98). The results of this research lead the authors to conclude that “the influence of English word-stock is pervasive, inasmuch as it extends into almost every field of Spanish vocabulary⁶. . . . Anglicisms are everywhere. Spanish is not immune to the growing phenomenon of English as a global language. It is, indeed, a tendency that will certainly continue in the future” (de la Cruz Cabanillas and Tejedor Martínez 2012, 112).

3. Methodology

The present article displays a study based on the anglicisms collected by Delia Rodríguez Segura (1998) in her PhD thesis. This work has been chosen because its author provides us with the most comprehensive list of anglicisms in Spanish from recent times. First, a selection from the words she compiles is made, in accordance with the series of criteria listed below. Then, the searches for these anglicisms are performed in the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual (CREA)*. Finally, a compilation of data on the thematic fields in relation to the anglicisms that are found in each of them is carried out. The possibility of establishing certain filters offered by the *CREA* makes it feasible to refine the search according to the following parameters:

- Chronology: 2001 – 2004
- Medium: Newspapers
- Geography: Spain

With respect to the chronological period established, it must be remembered that Rodríguez Segura (1998) compiled her database of anglicisms in the 1990s. Thus, the years 2001–2004, which came immediately afterwards, constitute a reasonable period within which to check the actual contexts of use of the English loanwords she collected. Furthermore, this temporal selection is relevant because it

refers to the first four years of the 21st century. They are the only years belonging to the current century that are included in the *CREA*. The possibility of using the *Corpus del Español del Siglo XXI (CORPES XXI)* was considered, since it covers more recent texts – the time span of this corpus now includes the period from 2001 to 2012. However, this option was finally rejected because, in relation to the thematic classification, it considers only general fields, whereas the *CREA* divides these broader categories into subfields as well. Due to the fact that this study intended to focus on areas such as *sports* or *computing* (that appeared in the lower level of the taxonomy), the latter corpus was chosen, the priority here being to investigate the thematic domains in greater depth.

As far as the medium is concerned, the press was selected as the source for texts because journalese characterizes fairly closely the state of the language a speech community possesses at a given moment and, at the same time, it fosters the spread of neologisms that have been coined recently (Luján García 1999; Furiassi 2008; Medina López 2004; del Pino Romero 2013; Oncins-Martínez 2012; Casado Velarde 2015).

On the matter of the geographical area, Spain was selected due to its location. Since the present piece of research intended to cover the press published in a non-English-Spanish-bilingual country, the US and the Philippines could not have been chosen. Latin America was an option, of course, but rather than randomly selecting from the various countries that make it up, the single country of Spain was settled on.

Therefore, taking Rodríguez Segura's (1998) list as a starting point, it was determined to search for instances of the anglicisms she collected in order to analyse real cases in which they have been employed relatively recently in the Spanish contemporary press. It should be noted here that a selection of the anglicisms provided by Rodríguez Segura (1998) in Appendix I of her thesis was made, leaving aside the following ones:

- Lexical anglicisms that she collected only from oral mass media. (She gives their phonetic transcription and their English spelling form or the standard Spanish one. Thus, since the focus of the present study is on written Spanish, these cases are irrelevant to its purposes.)
- What Rodríguez Segura (1998) calls “calco fraseológico” (phraseological calques): exclamations, interjections, adverbial and prepositional expressions and locutions, conversational formulae, idiomatic expressions, fixed phrases, etc. Pragmatic elements are outside the scope of this study.
- Paronymic semantic anglicisms (those cases in which the meaning of a Spanish word is influenced by that of an English one, and thus it acquires a new sense, a sense its English paronym bears) and semantic calques (those instances in which the English model is translated, and there is no direct etymological relationship between the English word and its Spanish rendering, although the two can have the same “étimo último”⁷, for example, *to channel/ canalizar*).

- Abbreviations with no specification as to what they stand for.

After performing the searches for all the anglicisms (a total amount of 2,198), the concordances obtained were classified in terms of thematic field. It is necessary to clarify that it does not refer to the domain in which the anglicism would itself be located, but to the one where the text in which it appears has been placed in the *CREA* (see Appendix).

4. Results and discussion

The present study focuses on the 93 subfields of the classification provided in the *CREA* (i.e. those registered on the right-hand column of Table 1). Out of them, 86 show the presence of English loanwords. Due to space constraints, only the first 30 topic areas in the ranking (i.e. those with a higher number of tokens) are included in Table 2. In relation to the types (i.e. the different anglicisms that are employed in the texts belonging to each thematic field), the list of those appearing in the aforementioned 30 topic areas are displayed in Appendix.

The five fields located in the upper part of Table 2 are *sports*, *music*, *politics*, *computing*, and *cinema and video*. The following paragraphs offer some possible reasons for these results.

In relation to the domain which seems to be most inclined to feature anglicisms, the fact that most modern sports games are of Anglo-North American origin (cf. Rodríguez González 2012, 318) can be considered as the main motivating factor for its position in the classification. Those activities entered the recipient society accompanied by their original names. Since these games were unknown in Spanish-speaking countries before, no equivalents for the words that denominated them existed there. Consequently, when these activities were introduced, the two possible options were either to adopt their foreign names or to calque them into the receptor language. The findings obtained in this research (on texts dated from 2001 to 2004), which indicate that the sports domain is in top position, coincide with the results got by Domínguez Mejías (2002), who in fact establishes a classification according to the thematic areas where anglicisms are present in the 22nd ed. (2001) of the *DRAE* and concludes that the dominant field is sports. Accordingly, it may be posited that there is a correlation between the number of entries devoted to anglicisms related to sports in the *DRAE* (at least, in its 22nd ed.) and the number of texts dealing with sports that contain anglicisms in contemporary usage (2001–2004): the domain where they are actually most numerous is the most represented in the Academic Dictionary (*DRAE* 2001).

Moreover, the place of *sports* as the area taking in most anglicisms in the European Spanish press is also shared by another geographical variety of the same language. Indeed, Sánchez Fajardo's (2016) study of Cuban Spanish reveals that *sports* is also the field in which anglicisms appear most frequently.⁸ What

is more, other languages are known to exhibit this characteristic too. In Seidel's (2010) systematic analysis, from a corpus-based perspective, of "the quantitative as well as the qualitative usage of English loanwords in the language of the German press" (Seidel 2010, 3), *sports* turns out to be the most common thematic category. In Andersen's (2011) distribution by domain of anglicisms appearing in the *Norwegian Newspaper Corpus*, the top position of the classification is also held by *sports* (42%).

The second place is occupied by *music*. As Luján García (2012) underlines, this sphere is very susceptible to English influence. This author points out that, nowadays, there are Spanish singers who compose and sing in English rather than in their mother tongue. These bands, that have English instead of Spanish names as well, have mainly two reasons for singing in English: first, since English is perceived as trendy, they employ it to look 'cool' and fashionable; second, this language allows them to address a major audience. In addition, most radio stations in Spain broadcast music in English and, moreover, others include different types of programmes exclusively in this foreign tongue. As concerns the spread of music-domain English to other languages, there is some evidence from Norwegian. Andersen (2011) claims that *music* is in the third out of eight classificatory positions as regards the distribution of the most frequent anglicisms appearing in the *Norwegian Newspaper Corpus*. (However, it should be noted that there is a significant difference between the first (42%) and second (33%) positions, on the one hand, and the third (8%), on the other hand.)

Surprisingly, *politics* outranks *computing* in the standings delineated in the present analysis. To my knowledge, only Seidel (2010), when studying the use of anglicisms in the German press, has reported on the field of *politics* as a thematic area susceptible to the introduction of English loanwords: this author maintains that the most frequent domain is *sports*, followed by *culture and education*, *economics and finance*, *sciences and technology*, and *politics and society*.

In the fourth position is *computing*. This field is constantly developing and launching innovations, which are carried out mainly in the US; hence, the new programmes, devices, etc. are given English names, and these are adopted into the Spanish vocabulary which is associated with the objects and concepts they refer to. Since the number of new technological items related to computer science is great, and unendingly appearing, many scholars have dealt with the influence of English on the Spanish language in this field, analysing it from various perspectives. Thus, the following works concentrate on this issue: Gallench and Posteguillo (2001), Posteguillo (2002), Cerdá Redondo et al. (2005), Munday (2005), Morin (2006), Tejedor Martínez et al. (2006), Díez Prados et al. (2007), Andersson (2008), Bolaños-Medina and Luján-García (2010), de la Cruz Cabanillas and Tejedor Martínez (2012), and Alcalde and Gregorio Cano (2013).

Cinema and video, as a pair, fall into the fifth place. The fact that films can deal with a wide range of subjects makes it possible for the texts focusing

on cinema and video to contain quite a large number of anglicisms relating to a variety of issues (see Appendix).⁹ Nevertheless, some of the loanwords appearing in these texts belong, specifically, to the cinematographic area. In fact, as García Morales (2009, 12) asserts, “la estrecha relación entre la influencia del cine norteamericano en España y el empleo de voces procedentes del inglés en español es innegable”.

The kind of analysis carried out in the present study offers the possibility of establishing which thematic areas more frequently accept anglicisms. Until recently, much research in this area has been guesswork, but today electronic corpora make it possible to confirm intuitions by examining hundreds or thousands of real cases (Oncins-Martínez 2012).

Table 1. Thematic classification in *CREA*: fields and subfields

ARTS	Antiques; Architecture; Arts and culture in general; Craftmanship; Cinema and video; Dance; Design; Theatre; Sculpture; Different shows; Photography; Mass media; Music; Painting; Advertising
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	Astronomy, Biology; Biochemistry; Botany; Sciences and technology; Ecology; Electronics; Energy; Statistics; Physics; Geology; Different industries; Computing; Engineering; Mathematics; Meteorology; Chemistry; Technology; Veterinary science; Zoology and paleontology
SOCIAL SCIENCES, BELIEFS AND THOUGHTS	Anthropology; Archeology; Astrology and occultism; Civilization, Ethnology; Education; Eroticism, Sexology; Ethics; Philosophy; Folklore; Geography; History; Linguistics and language; Literature; Mythology; Women; Psychology; Religion; Sociology; Different documents; Town planning
LEISURE TIME, DAILY LIFE	Current affairs; Hobbies; Household issues; Customs; Sports; Gastronomy, cookery; Gardening; Games; Fashion; Taumachy; Tourism; Housing
POLITICS, ECONOMICS, COMMERCE AND FINANCE	Commerce; Law; Development; Economics and public purse; Army, Military science; Employment, jobs; Companies; Government; Church; Industry; Justice, Legislation; Marketing; Business; Politics; Civil defence; Social security; Traffic; European Union
HEALTH	Biomedicine; Pharmacology; Medicine; Homeopathic medicine; Nutrition; Psychiatry; Health; Public health

Table 2. The 30 highest-ranking topics and the number of tokens for each

	Topic	Tokens of anglicisms
1	Sports	3902
2	Music	1372
3	Politics	1196
4	Computing	880
5	Cinema and video	831
6	Justice, legislation	568
7	Army, military science	464
8	Sciences and technology	436
9	Current affairs	392
10	Mass media	388
11	Economics and public purse	303
12	Tourism	291
13	Medicine	289
14	Town planning	230
15	Health	220
16	Arts and culture in general	217
17	Different industries	207
18	Civil defence	200
19	Literature	190
20	Theatre	190
21	Technology	162
22	Education	157
23	Different documents	155
24	Companies	131
25	Business	119
26	Gastronomy, cookery	114
27	History	111
28	Games	102
29	Astronomy	99
30	Fashion	91

With respect to the hypothesis stated at the beginning of this discussion, that *Sports, computing, economics, advertising and tourism are the topics in which anglicisms are more frequently employed*, it is seen that only two out of these five areas have been proved to be included among the top five fields in the ranking.

Indeed, the thematic domain in which anglicisms are employed most frequently in Spanish is *sports*. *Computing* occupies the fourth place in the scale, *music* and *politics* ranking in the second and third places, respectively. The fifth one is for *cinema and video*. *Economics (and public purse)* is located in the 11th position, whereas *tourism* appears in the 12th place of the classification. Surprisingly, *advertising* is not even among the top 30 thematic areas in terms of tokens of anglicisms employed (see Table 2).

5. Conclusions

As Medina López ([1996] 2004, 27) states, the use of anglicisms is not a homogeneous issue; it can only be understood if viewed in terms of a variety of lexical fields. By using corpus analysis in an approach to the employment of English loanwords in journalese, it has been possible to demonstrate, on evidence from a large number of texts, which lexical fields, or topic areas, take in most anglicisms. Needless to say, the results obtained in this study represent tendencies and cannot confidently be generalized, since they are based on a limited collection of texts. Still, because the corpus analysed is a representative and balanced sample of the Spanish contemporary press (including 55 different sources), the findings may be considered a reliable reflection of Spanish journalese during the span under consideration (2001–2004). The section of the *CREA* employed (2001–2004, Spain, newspapers, all topics) consists of as many as 5,836,589 words.

Furthermore, although the anglicisms examined have been limited to those collected by Rodríguez Segura (1998), and others surely occur in the journalistic texts stored in the *CREA* (2001–2004, Spain, all topics), the sum of individual anglicisms searched for numbers to 2,198,¹⁰ a figure which constitutes a significant set of English loanwords.

As regards the 93 thematic areas into which texts are classified in the *CREA*, 86 of them feature one or more anglicisms in at least one of their documents. In descending order, *sports*, *music*, *politics*, *computing*, and *cinema and video* are the fields boasting the higher concentrations of relevant evidence.

Thus, *music* and *politics* occupy the second and third places, respectively, according to the data culled and adduced here. However, these topic areas have scarcely been treated in the existing literature on anglicisms in Spanish. In contrast, *fashion*, a widely studied topic, appears here well down the list in the 30th place. It is also surprising that *business*, a field supposedly rife with anglicisms, ranks 25th. Admittedly, this alternate ranking may be due to a difference in the parameters considered for the inclusion of words: whereas most previous studies have included in their compilations only those loanwords which themselves belong to a certain thematic domain (irrespective of the thematic area of the texts within which the loans occur), the present piece of research takes into account the

thematic area of the texts where the anglicisms registered by Rodríguez Segura (1998) appear.

The findings obtained in the present study warns us about the necessity of carrying out further analyses of the use of English loanwords in the areas of *music*, *politics*, and *cinema and video* (for instance, in various newspapers as well as in the supplements that some of them publish) in order to go more deeply into the presence of anglicisms in these socio-cultural thematic domains.

Finally, the use of the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual*, an electronic resource developed by the Real Academia Española, has provided this study of anglicisms in the Spanish press at the beginning of the 21st century with high reliability. Thanks to this corpus, it has been possible to obtain results in terms of frequency of use which have long been elusive.

Notes

- 1 The *CREA* is a representative and balanced corpus of the Spanish language, which is freely available at www.rae.es and stores one hundred and sixty million forms approximately. It consists of a vast number of texts extracted from different sources and held electronically. It covers a temporal span that goes from 1975 until 2004 and an array of oral (10%) as well as written (90%) texts produced in all the Spanish-speaking countries. The written part has been selected from books, newspapers, journals, magazines, and miscellaneous sources. Considering the sample extracted from the press, it includes a great variety of copies (of national as well as local newspapers, generalist and specialized ones, etc.).
- 2 On neologisms in this specialised field, Ainciburu (2003, 186) states that “[e]l problema más obvio de la producción neológica es el de la invasión por préstamo de los anglicismos, problema que se puede observar en todos los sectores del idioma, pero que es fundamental en el lenguaje económico”.
- 3 See above, Gerritsen et al. (2007). However, an unwonted case can be highlighted in the area of cleaning: the American product “Mr. Clean” (which belongs to Procter & Gamble; https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Don_Limpio), appeared in Spain as “Mr. Proper” (Rodríguez Segura 1998, ch.4.4.2.4.; this PhD thesis is not paginated), and it was its name for years. However, at a certain point in time, this English name was substituted by a Spanish one: the product has been called “Don Limpio” since that moment.
- 4 “Utilizaremos ahora los corpus de ambos trabajos (Coryn 2011 and Smessaert 2011), los cuales constituirán el corpus español utilizado para el presente trabajo. Ese corpus español lo contrastaremos con el mexicano, elaborado ese último para los fines específicos de la presente investigación” (Smessaert 2012, 12).
- 5 The use of anglicisms in Spanish touristic texts has also been dealt with in

works such as de la Cruz Cabanillas, Mancho Barés, and Tejedor Martínez (2009) and Rocamora Abellán (1999).

- 6 The authors point out that, although their corpus comprises documents belonging to specialised fields, “these texts very often contain articles dealing with other topics and thus we have recorded terms from general language, as well” (98).
- 7 For Pratt (1980), a landmark in the study of English borrowings adopted by Spanish, anglicisms are only those words whose “étimo inmediato” (i.e. the tongue from which they have been taken directly, no matter the languages in which they have been employed in their previous history; cf. “étimo último”, the first and most remote language in which the word was coined, normally Latin or Greek) is the English language. On the contrary, Lorenzo Criado (1996) collects words that come from English, directly or through other languages.
- 8 In this case, it is not just the press that has served as the source for obtaining the anglicisms; the author has consulted dictionaries, glossaries, web pages, newspapers, etc.
- 9 It must be kept in mind that, in the present piece of research, the classification in terms of fields corresponds to that included in the *CREA*: it is the texts that are disposed according to the subject they deal with; therefore, the allocation of a loanword within a certain thematic area does not depend on the field this word itself belongs to, but to the one the text (where it appears) fits in. Sometimes, the concept that a given anglicism points to in a given case is connected to the topic within which the text is classified (for example, when *club* refers to a football team, the text belongs to “sports”, while when this word appears in the term *club de alterne* it is found in a document referring to “justice, law”). Nevertheless, this connection is not always present. As a matter of fact, the *CREA* contains texts dealing with sports clubs involved in judicial issues, being the document included, thus, within the topic “justice, law” (see Appendix).
- 10 Out of them, there are 1,404 Anglicisms for which no concordances have been obtained in the *CREA* (2001 – 2004, Spain, press, all topics).

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Appendix

Topics and types in *CREA*

Topic	N. of types	List of Types
Sports	201	aeróbic, aire acondicionado, antidopaje, approach, ATP, autocar, autocares, bar, barbacoa, basket, béisbol, bicicleta de montaña, birdie, birdies, bogey, bogeys, boxeador, boxes, break, bus, cambiar el chip, cámping, campus, CD, challenge, chárter, chut, chutar, club, clubes, clubs, cocktail, cóctel, córner, córners, crack, cross, dandy, derby, dopado, dopaje, dopante, doparse, doping, dream team, drive, drop, DV, DVD, eagle, e-mail, eslogan, esquí, esquiador, estándar, estrellato, estrés, fan, fans, fax, FBI, feeling, filmar, fitness, folclore, fútbol, futbolista, gadgets, gay, gays, glamour, gol, goleada, goleador, goles, golf, golfista, green, guru, hándicap, hobby, hockey, hooligans, iceberg (ser algo la punta del iceberg), indoor, internet, inusual, jersey, judo, junior, juniors, kart, kick boxing, killer, láser, líder, liderar, liderato, liderazgo, líderes, light, manager, managers, marketing, márketing, match, mediático, minimalista, misil, misiles, mister, mountain bike, NASA, off, OTAN, outdoor, parking, pedigrí, penalti, penalty, play, playboy, play-off, play-offs, póker, pole, pole position, pop, prensa amarilla, pub, pubs, putter, putts, rally, rallye, rallyes, rallies, ranking, rap, reality show, récord, relax, rifle, ring, robot, robotizar, rol, round, rugby, scooter, senior, seniors, set, sets, show, sida, sir, skate, ski, slalom, snow, snowboard, spots, sprint, squash, standard, step, street, stretching, surf, suspense, swing, tee, teléfono, televisión, tenis, tenista, test, tie break, tobogán, top ten, transfer, transfér, trial, túnel, turismo, turista, turística, turístico, USA, versus, videojuego, village, vip, VIP, warm-up, waterpolo, web, whisky, yanqui, yanquis
Music	230	acid, afro, aire acondicionado, alta fidelidad, ambient, amplificador, arty, background, bar, base de datos, beat, bermudas, big band, blues, bluesman, bluesy, boom, break, breakdance, brit, british, brothers, cambiar el chip, cámpings, cannabis, cásting, CD, CD's, chat, climax, club, clubes, clubs, CNN, cóctel, cool, correo electrónico, country, crack, dance, dandy, disc-jockey, disco compacto, disco duro, dólar, drogadicción, DVD, elepé, elepés, e-mail, en vivo, esnobista, establishment, estándar, estándares, estrellato, fan, fans, fashion, feeling, filme, flash, FM, folclor, folclórica, folclórico, folk, folklore, folklórica, folklórico, funk, funky, fútbol, futbolista, gay, gays, GB,

		<p>gentleman, gin-tonic, glam, glamour, glamouroso, goles, golf, gospel, grammy, grunge, gueto, hall, happy hour, hard, hard rock, hardware, heavy, heavy metal, hip hop, hippies, hippy, hobby, hooligans, house, iceberg (ser algo la punta del iceberg), indie, interactivo, internet, inusual, jazz, jazzístico, jazzman, jazz-rock, jet, kitsch, láser, líder, liderar, líderes, lounge, LP, LPs, made in, management, manager, managers, marketing, márketing, MB, mediático, merchandising, mini-CD, minidisc, minimal, minimalismo, minimalista, misiles, mixtura, multimedia, music hall, noise, on, on line, out, pack, parking, party, PC, pedigrí, performance, performances, play back, playback, playboy, plug-ins, póker, pop, pop-rock, póster, power, pub, punk, punk-rock, rap, rapero, récord, reggae, remix, reverb, revival, riffs, ring, rock, rock and roll, rockabilly, rockero, rol, saloon, sampler, samplers, saxofón, set, sexy, show, show business, showman, sida, single, singles, sir, ska, snowboard, software, soul, spot, standard, star, step, stoniano, surf, swing, techno, tecno, teléfono, televisión, test, tex- mex, thrash, tiempo parcial, a, tocadiscos, trailers, trash, trip, tripphop, tripi, túnel, turismo, turística, turístico, underground, UNESCO, unisex, videoclip, vinilo, vip, walkman, web, West End, whisky, yanqui, yanquis, yonkis, yuppies</p>
Politics	153	<p>aislacionista, alta fidelidad, apartheid, bar, base de datos, béisbol, bingo, blue jeans, body (el body), boicot, boicoteo, bulldozers, búnker, búnkeres, cámping, campus, chequear, CIA, ciberpunk, clan, club, clubes, CNN, cocktail, cóctel, consultoría, correo electrónico, cowboy, crooner, dandy, dólar, downtown, DVD, en vivo, eslogan, esquí, esquiar, establishment, estándares, fair play, fax, FBI, flash, folclore, folclórica, folclórico, fútbol, futbolista, gasóleo, gay, gays, gente guapa, gol, goleada, goles, golf, gong, hacker, hall, hockey, homeless, iceberg (ser algo la punta del iceberg), implementar, internet, inusual, IRA, jeans, jet, láser, líder, liderar, liderazgo, líderes, light, lobby, lores, marine, marines, marketing, márketing, master, mediático, mercadeo, misil, misiles, mitin, mítin, number one, off the record, on line, OTAN, parking, piercing, play, pop, póquer, póster, power, premier, prime time, privacidad, pubs, puzzle, radar, realidad virtual, récord, robot, rock, rockero, rol, round, rugby, sandwich, sauna, senior, seniors, SIDA, sir, skin, slogan, software, spot, spots, sprint, squash, stablishment, status, suspense, tabloide, tabú, teléfono, televisión, test, tetra-brik, tories, tormenta de ideas, trailer, túnel, turismo, turista, turística, turístico, USA, video, VIH, vs, walkie (talkie), water, web, whisky, WWF, yanqui, yogur</p>

Computing	108	aerolínea, banners, bar, base de datos, bits, bloc, boom, browser, buffer, bus, bytes, caché, cannabis, CD, CD-ROM, chat, chequeo, chip, clubes, CNN, comida basura, computador, computadora, consultoría, cookies, copyright, correo electrónico, CPU, disco compacto, disco duro, disquete, disquetes, dólar, drive, driver, DVD, e-mail, escáner, estándar, estándares, fans, fax, FBI, filme, flash, formatear, freeware, fútbol, GB, golf, gong, hardware, hobby, hockey, http, implementar, indexar, interfaz, internet, láser, líder, liderar, líderes, marketing, MB, megabytes, microsoft, módem, multimedia, NASA, on, on line, party, PC, plug and play, plug-in, plug-ins, póker, pop, privacidad, punk-rock, radar, RAM, ranking, récord, removible, RISC, robot, robótica, rock, shareware, sida, software, stand, teléfono, televisión, test, touch, turismo, turística, turístico, UNESCO, versus, video, videoclip, videojuego, web, zoom
Cinema and video	188	(en) off, aislacionismo, arty, asesino en serie, bar, barbacoa, base de datos, basket, béisbol, bikini, bits, body (el body), boom, boxeador, casting, CD, CD-ROM, CIA, cinemscope, clan, click, clip, club, CNN, cóctel, comic, cool, correo electrónico, country, crack, crooner, dandi, dólar, drogadicto, DV, DVD, electroshock, e-mail, en el aire, escáner, eslogan, esnifar, estrellato, estrés, fan, fans, fashion victim, FBI, feeling, film, filmación, filmar, filme, filmes, films, flash, flashes, folk, folklore, friqui, full contact, full time, fútbol, futbolista, gag, gags, gay, gays, glamour, gol, golf, gore, hacker, hip hop, hippy, hockey, hooligans, indie, internet, inusual, IRA, jazz, jeep, jetlag, karts, kit, kitsch, líder, líderes, loft, look, made in, magazine, marca de fábrica, mediático, minimalismo, miss, mister, mitin, off, on, on line, oscar, out, outsider, PC, performances, póker, polaroid, pop, póquer, prime time, privacidad, pub, punch, punk, rafting, rapero, récord, remake, remakes, rifle, ring, road movie, robótica, rock, rol, rugby, sampleado, sex-symbol, share, sheriff, show, showman, sida, skate, skateboard, sketch, sketches, sketches, slang, smoking, snowboard, software, soul, sport, spot, spots, star system, starlettes, status, street, strip-tease, surf, surfista, suspense, tabú, tandem, teenager, telefilme, teléfono, televisión, tenis, test, thriller, top model, trailer, trailers, trash, trekkie, túnel, turismo, underground, UNESCO, USA, versus, video, videoclub, vinilo, web, West Village, western, westerns, whisky, yanqui, yanquis, zapping, zombies
Justice, legislation	128	adicción (a las drogas), antidopaje, approach, asesino en serie, bar, base de datos, beatle, béisbol, boicot, boom, cabezas

		rapadas, caché, campus, cannabis, casting, CD, CD's, chárter, chat, chequeo, chip, CIA, clan, club, clubes, clubs, CNN, cóctel, comida rápida, copyright, correo electrónico, country, data-mining, disc-jockey, disco duro, disquetes, dólar, dopado, dopaje, drogadicción, DVD, e-mail, escáner, eslogan, esquí, estándar, estándares, estrés, fax, FBI, ferry, film, filmar, folk, fútbol, futbolista, gasóleo, gay, gays, heavy metal, hobby, holding, hooligans, iceberg (ser algo la punta del iceberg), interactivo, internet, inusual, IRA, lady, láser, líder, liderar, liderazgo, líderes, lifting, marines, mediático, misil, misiles, mitin, on, on line, OTAN, out, overbooking, parking, PC, piercing, playboy, pop, premier, privacidad, pub, puzzles, rallye, ranking, rap, reality, reality show, récord, revólver, rifle, robot, rock, rockero, scanner, sex-shop, skin, software, spray, status, tabloide, teléfono, televisión, télex, tenis, test, trailer, trailers, túnel, turismo, turista, turística, turístico, web, whisky, yanqui, yanquis
Army, military science	56	aire acondicionado, autocar, bar, base de datos, briefing, búnker, campus, cascos azules, CIA, CNN, cóctel, cowboy, dólar, eslogan, estrés, FBI, filmación, filmar, finger, flash, fútbol, gángster, internet, intranet, inusual, IRA, jeep, jersey, líder, liderar, liderazgo, líderes, lobby, marine, marines, misil, misiles, OTAN, póker, premier, privacidad, puzzle, radar, radares, rafting, rifle, robot, rol, teléfono, televisión, test, túnel, turística, video, web, yanqui
Science and technology	105	aire acondicionado, base de datos, bicicleta de montaña, bits, búnker, caché, campus, CD, CD-ROM, chat, chip, CIA, CNN, consultoría, correo electrónico, CPU, discman, disco compacto, disco duro, DV, DVD, e-mail, en vivo, escanear, escáner, eslogan, estándar, estándares, estrés, fans, fax, faxes, FBI, filmar, filme, freelance, fútbol, GB, gol, goles, hardware, hit parade, http, interactivo, interfaz, internet, intranet, junior, killer, kit, know-how, láser, líder, líderes, lord, made in, marketing, MB, mecadotecnia, minimalista, misiles, módem, multimedia, NASA, off, on, on line, party, PC, pecé, PIN, power, privacidad, radar, radares, rally, RAM, rap, realidad virtual, récord, rifle, robot, robótica, rock, script, sets, sida, single, software, spin, teléfono, televisión, tenis, test, trailer, transistor, turismo, turista, turística, versus, videojuego, walkie (talkie), walkman, web, zoom
Current affaires	126	aeróbic, aeroclub, aerolínea, aire acondicionado, autocar, baby boom, badminton, bar, base de datos, bicicleta de montaña, blues, boxeador, bus, campus, cannabis, CD, chip, clan, club, clubes, cool, correo electrónico, dandy,

		disc-jockey, disco duro, DVD, esquí, esquiador, esquiar, estándar, estrellato, estrés, fan, fans, fashion, feeling, filme, filmes, fitness, folclórico, footing, funk, fútbol, futbolista, gay, gays, glamour, godspell, goleada, goles, golf, hall, hip hop, hit, house, internet, inusual, IRA, jazz, jersey, jet, líder, liderazgo, líderes, lobby, look, magazines, managers, marketing, master, microchip, misil, miss, multimedia, NASA, OTAN, out, parking, pedigrí, penalti, performance, performances, play, playboy, pop, power, premier, privacidad, pub, pubs, puenting, rally, rallyes, rapero, rasta, récord, road movie, robot, rock, round, show, showman, soul, speaker, spot, stand, stop, surfing, tabloide, teléfono, televisión, tenis, tenista, top-less, túnel, turismo, turista, turística, turístico, USA, video, web, weekend, wonderbra, yogur, zapping
Mass media	62	CNN, (en) off, boicot, casting, cásting, club, clubes, clúster, comedia de situación, comunicacional, DVD, electroshock, eslogan, fans, fanzine, filmes, flash, FM, fútbol, gags, gays, glamour, goles, internet, jersey, líder, liderazgo, líderes, magazine, magazines, marketing, mediático, NASA, PC, penalti, póquer, prime time, priones, ranking, reality, reality show, récord, round, share, show, showman, sketches, sketches, suspense, talk show, teléfono, televisión, tenis, terminator, terminators, test, top ten, underground, USA, web, whisky, zapping
Economics and public purse	44	baby boom, boom, cash flow, CD, club, clubes, denim, dólar, eslogan, estándar, estándares, fax, fútbol, futbolista, gasóleo, glamour, hockey, holding, internet, líder, liderazgo, líderes, light, marketing, márketing, mister, PC, pop, ranking, récord, rol, senior, stocks, tandem, teléfono, televisión, test, tiempo completo, a, túnel, turismo, turística, turístico, USA, web
Tourism	44	aire acondicionado, apartheid, autocar, autocares, bar, batir un récord, bus, cámping, cátering, CD, club, clubes, correo electrónico, dólar, driblar, e-mail, folclor, folclórica, fútbol, gay, golf, hooligans, interactivo, jazz, kitsch, líder, liderar, líderes, récord, rock, stand, stop, surf, teléfono, televisión, turismo, turista, turística, turístico, video, videojuego, VIP, web, WWF
Medicine	48	base de datos, boom, chip, cociente intelectual, correo electrónico, dólar, dopante, en vivo, escáner, estándar, estándares, estandarización, estrés, estresante, fútbol, gays, hiper, inputs, interactivo, inusual, láser, líder, liderar, liderazgo, líderes, mix, on line, out, output, outputs, récord, rock, rol, scanner, sida, SIDA, software, standard, teléfono, televisión, test, trial, versus, VIH, vs, web, whisky, yogur

Town planning	42	autocares, baby boom, badminton, bar, bingo, boom, bungalows, bus, cámping, camping gas, campus, CD-ROM, club, clubes, comida rápida, correo electrónico, dúplex, fax, folclore, folklórico, footing, fútbol, gol, golf, hándicap, jacuzzi, líder, liderazgo, lord, pádel, parking, sauna, skate, stock, teléfono, televisión, tenis, test, túnel, turismo, turística, turístico
Health	66	adicción (a las drogas), aerobic, aire acondicionado, antidopaje, antiestrés, bar, bypass, by-pass, cannabis, chequeo, club, cóctel, comida rápida, computador, correo electrónico, crack, drogadicción, drogadicto, drogas de diseño, e-mail, escáner, estándar, estándares, estandarizar, estrés, estresante, finger, flash, FSH, fútbol, gasóleo, hippy, hockey, iceberg (ser algo la punta del iceberg), internet, inusual, láser, láseres, lavavajillas, lentes de contacto, líder, liderazgo, líderes, light, OTAN, PC, peeling, piercing, pub, ranking, rol, sandwichera, SIDA, sida, software, teléfono, televisión, tenis, test, turismo, turista, turística, VIH, web, whisky, yonquis
Arts and culture in general	99	aeróbic, bar, base de datos, blues, body art, boom, campus, clown, club, clubes, cocktail, compact disc, correo electrónico, cyborg, dealers, drogadicto, DV, DVD, e-mail, en vivo, eslogan, estándar, fashion, fast food, FBI, film, filme, filmes, FM, folclore, folk, funky, fútbol, gay, gays, goles, gueto, hall, hamburguesa, happening, hardware, hip hop, hiper, interactivo, interfaz, internet, inusual, jazz, kitsch, líder, líderes, magazines, marketing, mass media, master, mediático, minimal, minimalismo, minimalista, multimedia, off, offset, on, on line, PC, performance, performances, pop, pop-rock, privacidad, pub, punk, puzzle, récord, revival, revólver, robótica, rock, rol, sexy, soft, software, stablishment, stand, superstar, tabú, teléfono, televisión, tenista, turismo, underground, UNESCO, USA, video, videoclip, videojuego, web, whisky, yogur
Different industries	76	ABS, acre, aerolínea, airbag, aire acondicionado, bar, base de datos, boom, bus, campus, cátering, CD, CD-ROM, charter, chip, club, cóctel, compost, correo electrónico, cross, disco compacto, dólar, DVD, en vivo, escúter, escúteres, estándar, estandarización, estrés, ferry, fútbol, gasóleo, holding, implementar, input, intercooler, internet, joint venture, kit, líder, liderar, liderazgo, líderes, lifting, light, lobby, marketing, multimedia, NASA, off, overbooking, parking, pick up, radar, rallies, récord, scooter, spoiler, stand, stocks, teléfono, telemárketing, televisión, toffee, toffees, top ten, trust, túnel, turismo, turista, turístico, USA, váteres, web, whisky, WWF

Civil defence	55	CNN, adicción (a las drogas), aerolínea, autocar, bar, béisbol, bikini, camping gas, chequeo, CIA, club, compact, crack, disquetes, drogas de diseño, esquí, esquiador, estándares, FBI, ferry, filmación, folclórica, fútbol, futbolista, gasoil, gasóleo, hiper, internet, jersey, ketchup, líder, liderar, líderes, marines, marketing, NASA, parking, privacidad, pub, pubs, radar, revólver, robot, speed, surf, teléfono, televisión, trailer, túnel, turismo, turista, turístico, video, web, whisky
Literature	98	aire acondicionado, aislacionista, approach, asesino en serie, autocares, bar, beat, bermudas, best-seller, boom, boxeador, boy, búnker, bus, campus, chip, CIA, click, club, cool, correo electrónico, crack, dandi, derby, disc-jockey, disquete, dólar, eslogan, esnob, esnobismo, estrés, fair play, fan, fans, fanzine, FBI, filmación, filmar, filme, filmes, flash, flashes, flirtear, folclore, free, fútbol, futbolista, gay, gays, gentleman, goleada, gueto, happy-, hard, hippies, hippy, internet, inusual, jazzístico, jeep, jogging, kitsch, líder, liderar, light, lord, mediático, mercadeo, mixtura, multimedia, PC, play, pop, póster, puzzle, realidad virtual, récord, rock, round, sketch, software, superstar, suspense, tabú, teléfono, televisión, tenis, thriller, tique, túnel, turf, turismo, turístico, USA, video, web, western, whisky
Theatre	86	afro, bar, body art, boxeador, break, campus, casting, clan, clown, clownesco, club, cluster, cóctel, comida rápida, computador, en vivo, fan, feeling, film, filmación, filme, filmes, flash, folclor, folclore, folclórica, folk, folklore, freaks, funk, funky, fútbol, gags, hall, hamburguesa, hip hop, hippie, hippy, interactivo, interfaz, internet, inusual, jazz, kart, líder, mediático, minimal, minimalista, misiles, multimedia, off, on, performance, performances, ping pong, play, pop, póquer, puzzle, ragtime, ranking, realidad virtual, revival, ring, robot, rock, rol, show, showman, sida, sketches, slalom, software, spots, standard, teléfono, televisión, thriller, transformers, túnel, UNESCO, USA, VIPs, vs, web, working
Technology	62	ABS, alta fidelidad, alto standing, amplificador, arcade, banners, bits, boom, caché, campus, CD, chip, computador, consultoría, correo electrónico, disco duro, disquetes, DVD, escáner, escáners, filmación, filmes, flash, FM, fútbol, GB, gigabytes, goles, hardware, high tech, iceberg (ser algo la punta del iceberg), interactivo, interfaz, internet, intranet, liderazgo, light, lobby, MB, módem, multimedia, NASA, on line, PC, pin, rail, RAM, récord, réflex, robot, software, standing, teléfono, televisión, terabyte, transistor, túnel, turismo, turística, videojuego, web, zoom

Education	56	aerobic, a tiempo parcial, autocares, bermudas, campus, CD, chat, cociente intelectual, correo electrónico, crack, discapacitado, disco compacto, DNA, e-mail, eslogan, estándar, estrés, estresante, feedback, fútbol, GMAT, interactivo, internet, intranet, inusual, jazz, judo, liderazgo, líderes, light, marketing, mass media, master, masters, MBA, mediático, multimedia, on line, PC, play back, priones, récord, robótica, rock, rol, sida, software, soul, suspense, teléfono, televisión, turismo, turístico, UNESCO, versus, web
Different documents	64	aire acondicionado, bar, bermudas, bulldozer, bus, camping, CD, clan, club, cóctel, electroshock, e-mail, esnob, esnobismo, estrés, fashion, footing, fútbol, futbolista, gay, gays, gol, goles, golf, hippie, hit, hobby, indi, internet, líder, líderes, lobby, made in, marketing, mediático, misil, misiles, off the record, panties, pop, póster, pub, pubs, punk, punkis, radar, récord, reggae, robótica, rock, show, sida, star, teléfono, televisión, tenis, top-less, tormenta de ideas, túnel, turismo, turística, video, walkie (talkie), yanquis
Companies	49	aerolínea, bonus, boom, cash, clan, club, consultoría, correo electrónico, dólar, e-business, esquí, estándares, fashion, fútbol, gasoil, gasóleo, glamour, goleada, golf, holding, inputs, internet, jeans, just-in-time, líder, liderar, liderazgo, lobby, made in, manager, marketing, MBA, multimedia, PC, ranking, récord, slip, software, status, stock, stocks, tandem, teléfono, televisión, tops, turismo, turística, turístico, web
Business	45	aerolínea, a tiempo parcial, beatle, búnker, business to business, campus, cash, catering, clan, clubes, computadora, consultoría, core, correo electrónico, dólar, eslogan, estándares, estrés, free float, fútbol, gasóleo, holding, hub, internet, joint venture, know-how, leasing, líder, liderar, liderazgo, líderes, marketing, master, mediático, on line, out, pop, privacidad, récord, stocks, teléfono, televisión, turismo, turístico, web
Gastronomy, cookery	55	bacon, bar, barman, base de datos, bol, boom, CD, club, clubes, cocktail, cóctel, comida rápida, correo electrónico, curry, dólar, donuts, en vivo, esquí, fútbol, ginger ale, hamburguesa, holding, interfaz, jazz, jet, lumpen, manager, marketing, mediático, minimalista, mixtura, PC, planning, pop, póquer, récord, sida, slip, sprint, stand, status, surf, teléfono, televisión, tetrabrick, tex-mex, the end, túnel, turismo, turístico, twist, village, web, whisky, yogurt
History	57	acre, a tiempo parcial, baby boom, bar, barbacoa, base de datos, boicot, búnkeres, CD, cheerleader, CIA, clan,

		club, copyright, DVD, estrés, estresante, FBI, ferry, filme, folclore, folclórico, folklore, folklórico, fútbol, iceberg (ser algo la punta del iceberg), inusual, jersey, líder, liderazgo, líderes, light, lobby, lumpen, marines, mediático, misiles, mitin, mixtura, on, OTAN, privacidad, pubs, ranking, récord, rol, sida, status, tabú, teléfono, televisión, tenis, turismo, turística, turístico, web, zoom
Games	37	arcade, bar, barbacoa, béisbol, boom, byte, CD, clan, club, computadora, drogas de diseño, DVD, estrés, fans, filme, golf, hacker, hardware, hip hop, interactivo, interfaz, marine, misiles, multimedia, on line, PC, puzzles, reality, rol, senior, software, suspense, tabloide, televisión, videojuego, web, zoom
Astronomy	25	airbag, chip, correo electrónico, dólar, e-mail, esquí, estándar, fans, filmar, filme, láser, multimedia, NASA, permafrost, pixel, pop, récord, robot, robótica, software, teléfono, turista, versus, video, web
Fashion	63	béisbol, bermudas, bits, boom, boxeador, cárdigan, cásting, cóctel, copyright, country, denim, disc-jockey, eslogan, esmoquin, estándar, eye-liner, fans, fashion, folclore, forever, fútbol, futbolista, gadgets, gay, glamour, hip hop, hippy, internet, jet, líder, look, master, new look, number one, off, patch, patchwork, piercing, play, pop, puzzle, rally, récord, rock, sexy, short, sir, skinheads, slip, sport, spots, stand, stretch, supermodelo, superwoman, teléfono, televisión, tenis, thriller, top-less, tops, turismo, web